

Review on Recent Advances in Synthesis of Black TiO₂

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Abstract:- Nanomaterials made of titanium dioxide (TiO₂) are commonly regarded as state-of-the-art photocatalysts for environmental remediation and energy conversion. Due of its unique electrical and optical characteristics, several attempts have been made to manufacture TiO₂ materials using various techniques. The electrical and optical characteristics of TiO₂ materials have long been investigated. The development of oxygen vacancies and Ti³⁺ defects in black TiO₂ has increased solar light absorption, promoted the separation of photo-generated charge carriers, and therefore improved photocatalytic activity in H₂ generation and pollutant degradation. A lattice disorder on the surface, as well as the presence of oxygen vacancies, Ti³⁺ ions, Ti-OH, and Ti-H groups, contribute to black TiO₂'s improved photocatalytic activity. Enhancing the optical absorption characteristics of TiO₂. In this article, we summarize the synthesis pathways, morphology and photocatalytic properties of Black titanium dioxide (TiO₂).

Keywords:- Synthesis pathways, Morphology, Photocatalysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Water covers 70% of the Earth, therefore it is reasonable to assume that it will always be plenty. Even still, potable water, which is utilized to irrigate our farm crops, is extremely scarce. Only 3% of the total available water on our planet is fresh water, and two-thirds of that is tucked away in glaciers or otherwise unavailable for humans to utilize. As a result, over 2.7 billion people face water scarcity for at least one month each year, and 1.1 billion people lack access to water globally.[1]

For 2.4 billion people, poor sanitation is a major worry, putting them at risk of diseases like cholera and typhoid fever, as well as other water-borne illnesses. Diarrhea kills two million people per year, the majority of them are children.. [2] All these are the negative impact of water because of its unavailability in many or the areas. If we focus now there are many ways to save water from wasting.

Water contamination is on the rise these days, thanks to rising population, industrialization, and urbanization. Chemical, petrochemical, pharmaceutical, and mining industries all demand enormous amounts of water. Ultrapure water is required in the pharmaceutical, microelectronics, and semiconductor sectors. Unfortunately, hazardous organic and inorganic substances contaminate the water discharged by these companies. [3] Toxic organic compounds such as chlorinated and non chlorinated aliphatic and aromatic compounds, dyes, detergents, and surfactants, agro wastes such as insecticides, pesticides, and herbicides, volatile organic compounds, plastics, inorganic compounds such as toxic metals, and pathogens such as bacteria, fungi, and virus are among the most common pollutants. All of this is wreaking havoc on the environment as well as living organisms. [4]

Water shortage is one of the world's most critical problems, and it will become more so in the future as the world's population and industry develop. Pollutants from diverse industries have recently been projected to have contaminated water to unsafe levels all around the world in the last two decades. These disrupt the environment's balance and inflict substantial harm to living organisms. Water is no longer an infinite resource, as people have realized.[5]. As a result, the necessity for innovative and effective water treatment processes for companies is clear. Today's fast increasing businesses produce a massive amount of chemical waste and effluent, much of which is illegally discharged into sea water or is treated in the CETP to some extent (Common Effluent Treatment Plant) [3] This treatment needs high amount of capital for investment and huge amount of land for equipment. It is necessary to use them because we can't let this much amount of water untreated and not to be transferred in sea or rivers as well. [5]

A. Toxicity in the Effluent Water

The full response of test organisms to all substances in wastewater is provided through toxicity evaluation, which is an important metric in wastewater quality monitoring.

Table 1 Toxicity evaluation [6]

Particulars	pH	BOD (mg/L)	COD (mg/L)	TSS (mg/L)	Nitrate (mg/L)	P (mg/L)
Untreated Waste Water	7.6	32	650	275	76	8
Treated Waste Water	8.01	20	40±1	15	13	2.5
Approved standards for discharge to surface water	6.5	30	60	40	50	6

B. Different Treatment Methods to treat Effluent

Mainly there are Four methods used for treatment of waste water

- Physical Treatment
- Biological Treatment
- Chemical Treatment
- Sludge Treatment

➤ *Physical Waste Water Treatment:-*

Physical methods are used to clean wastewater. Solids are removed through methods such as screening, sedimentation, and skimming, without chemicals. With sedimentation, insoluble/heavy particles are suspended from the waste water, and it is one of the most used physical wastewater treatment processes. [7]

Once the insoluble matter has gone to the bottom, you can separate the clear water. Another good physical water treatment method is aeration. This process includes pushing air through the water to supply oxygen. To eliminate all contaminants, the final stage, filtration is used. The most popular type of filter is the sand filter, Which can be applied to separate contaminants and insoluble particles from waste water. Sand filters are easily employed to remove oil from the surfaces of wastes.[8]

➤ *Biological Water Treatment:-*

This treatment involves various biological processes to break down the organic material present in wastewater, such as soap, human waste, oils and food. [9]Microorganisms metabolize organic matter in the wastewater in biological treatment. It can be divided into three categories: -

- Aerobic Process
- Anaerobic Process
- Composting

• *Aerobic process*

This process take place in presence of oxygen in which bacteria decomposes the organic matter and converts it into carbon dioxide that can be used by plants.

• *Anaerobic process*

The process take place in absence of oxygen. And in this Fermentation is used for fermenting the waste at specific temperature.

• *Composting*

This method involves mixing wastewater with sawdust or other carbon sources and it is a aerobic treatment. Although secondary treatment removes the majority of particles in wastewater, certain dissolved nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus may remain.

➤ *Chemical Water Treatment:-*

According to its name, this treatment uses chemicals in water to kill microorganisms that degrade water. Chloride is a typical oxidizing agent used to kill these microorganisms [10] Chemicals prevent bacteria from growing in water, resulting in pure water. If an acid or base is used to bring water to its neutral PH of 7, it is called neutralization.

➤ *Sludge Treatment:-*

Separation of solid and liquid phases is a solid-liquid process in which the solid phase must have minimum moisture, while the liquid phase separated must have minimal solid particles.

Dewatering of sludge from industrial wastewater or sewage plants is an example of this, where the residual moisture in the dewatered solid determines disposal costs and the pollution load returned to the treatment facility is determined by the cent rate quality.[11]

To remove the solids from the wastewater, a solid-liquid separation device such as a centrifuge is utilised. Wastewater has a big impact on the environment, so it's crucial to treat it properly. You not only safeguard the organisms that live on it, but you also protect the earth as a whole by cleaning wastewater. [12]

C. What is Photocatalysis?

Fig 1 Schematic diagram of Photocatalysis [13]

When a light source interacts with the surface of semiconductor materials, referred to as photocatalysts, photocatalysis occurs.[2] During this process, there must be at least two simultaneous reactions occurring, oxidation from photogenerated holes, and reduction from photogenerated electrons.

A material that is capable of absorbing light, producing electron-hole pairs undergo chemical transformation is known as Photocatalyst. There are Many Photocatalysts reported in literature such as TiO₂, CeO₂, SnO₂ etc. Among all these TiO₂ is extensively used Photocatalyst. [3], [4]

The photocatalyst itself should not undergo change and therefore a precise synchronization of the two processes needs to take place. In 1972 Fujishima and Honda were the first to demonstrate water electrochemical photocatalysis at a semiconductor electrode. [5] Later it was discovered that TiO₂ aids in decomposing cyanide in water, rising interest towards the material’s environmental applications. TiO₂ is suitable for photocatalysis for several reasons, some of which are its common availability, relatively low cost, and high chemical stability. [14]

Photocatalysis can be used to degrade contaminants and improve the quality of the atmosphere's air in a real-world setting. As a result, photocatalysis can be employed in the construction industry to improve indoor air quality. It's a chemical reaction triggered by photo absorption in a Photocatalyst that doesn't alter during the reaction. It is a "green" technology that operates at room temperature and pressure and uses a light source and oxygen from the air. [15] The capacity of the catalyst to make electron-hole pairs, which generate free radicals capable of subsequent reactions, is essential for photocatalytic activity.

D. Mechanism of Photocatalysis

The basic photocatalytic mechanism is as shown in figure 3. It includes the following steps.

[1] When absorption of energy (Photons) having energy greater than the band gap of photocatalyst then transfer of electrons takes place from valence band to conduction band. These leads to creation of holes (h⁺) in valence band. [16]

Fig 2 Schematic of Mechanism of Photocatalysis[13]

[2] These holes and electrons can recombine and release the absorbed energy in the form of heat.

[3] These electrons and holes then react with available oxidants and reductants to form powerful and unstable radicals.[16]

[4] Then these free radicals react with pollutants and degraded into carbon dioxide and water.

E. Titanium Dioxide (TiO₂)

Titanium dioxide is widely used photocatalyst because of its superior optical and electronic properties. It has a melting point of **1,843°C** and a boiling point of **2,972°C**, so it occurs as a solid in nature and, even in its particle form, it is insoluble in water. Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is a naturally occurring oxide of titanium. It is also referred to as titanium (IV) oxide or titania. TiO₂ is a cheap and widely available white oxide material having a molecular mass of 79.86 g/mol, a density of 3.9–4.2 g/cm³, a refractive index in the range of 2.5–2.75, and Mohs hardness of 5.5–7 [17]. There are three naturally occurring crystalline phases of TiO₂: anatase, rutile, and brookite. Anatase and rutile have a tetragonal structure, whereas brookite has an orthorhombic structure. For industrial applications, the anatase and rutile phases are the only ones commonly used. [18]. TiO₂ is a semiconductor, with a band gap of 3.2 eV for anatase and

3.0 eV for rutile. TiO_2 is a non-toxic, chemically stable, non-flammable, and biocompatible material. It can also be used as a white pigment. During the past few decades, exploration of nanomaterials has grown rapidly since nanosized materials demonstrate completely different properties from their bulk counterparts. As a result, TiO_2 is one of the most widely used nanomaterials and is useful in a wide range of applications [19].

Titania (TiO_2) is a white oxide ceramic having three crystalline forms: rutile, which has a tetragonal structure, anatase, which has a tetragonal structure as well, and brookite, which has an orthorhombic structure. Although most TiO_2 on the market is white in colour, it has another feature that is synthesised from the white TiO_2 . [17]

F. Limitations of TiO_2 Photocatalyst:-

- It is not sufficient to utilize maximum visible light.
- High e-h recombination rate.
- Low adsorption of Organic pollutants.
- Aggregation of NPs.
- Difficulties in recovering of NPs.
- Poor thermal stability (Anatase).

G. White TiO_2

- It is the most promising Sunlight Harvester.
- It has a band gap of 3.2 eV.
- It is cheap, non-toxic, photolytically and chemically stable also reusable with high turnover rate.
- Its physical and chemical modification is simple and easy to understand.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Hydrogenation Method

Mao and his co-workers [6] described a new method for making disordered nanophase TiO_2 by hydrogenating TiO_2 and adding a dopant. They made nanophase TiO_2 by heating a precursor solution including Titanium tetraisopropoxide, ethanol, HCl, and Pluronic F127 at 480°C for one day, then evaporating and drying it at 110°C for 24 hours, and finally calcining it at 500°C for 6 hours.

They claimed that hydrogenation of TiO_2 at 20 bars and 200°C for 5 days produced a disordered surface layer that shifted optical absorption from ultraviolet to near infrared. Furthermore, the band gap of hydrogenated black TiO_2 was around 1.0 eV, which was significantly lower than the 3.3 eV. They discovered that hydrogenated black TiO_2 has high activity and stability for photocatalytic hydrogen generation from water. The rate of hydrogen production was double that of previous semiconductor photocatalysts.

Li et. [20] reported on the effects of hydrogen treatment on the photocatalytic activities of rutile TiO_2 nanowire arrays with diameters of 100-200 nm. They discovered that as the temperature increased, the colour of hydrogen-treated TiO_2

nanowire films changed from white to yellowish green at 350°C and black at 450°C. Photocurrent densities were also two times higher in hydrogenated TiO_2 nanowire samples than in pure TiO_2 . They stated that the density of photocurrent increases as the temperature of hydrogen annealing rises.

Huang et.al [21] reported effect of hydrogen treatment on the activity of anatase TiO_2 . They discovered that hydrogen production rates were 3.2 to 3.8 times greater with hydrogenated TiO_2 than with air-treated TiO_2 and commercial P25. Mullins et al. [40] recently observed a synergistic effect after co-treating TiO_2 nanowire arrays with H_2 and NH_3 , significantly improving water photo-oxidation performance under visible light illumination.

Fig 3 Unmodified White and Hydrogenated black TiO_2

B. Chemical Reduction Methods

➤ NaBH_4 Reduction

Wenzhang Fang et.al [22] reported NaBH_4 reduction that was used to prepare Ti^{+3} self-doped TiO_2 . They created a series of TiO_2 nanoparticles called m- TiO_2 (Where m denotes the amount of NaBH_4 added). The synthesized material was then calcined for 3 hours at 500°C in a muffle furnace. They discovered that the photocatalytic activity of self-doped TiO_2 with Ti^{+3} is proportional to the doped Ti^{+3} . Because of the increased BET surface area after HCL washing, the produced catalyst demonstrated stronger visible light photocatalytic activity than before.

➤ CaH_2 Reduction method

Guilian Zhu et. al [23] reported CaH_2 reduction method for black TiO_2 synthesis with increased photocatalytic decontamination and water splitting performances at low temperatures. They demonstrated that TiO_2 was reduced to

Ti₂O₃ using the reducing agent CaH₂. The use of metal hydride to reduce transition metal oxides at low temperatures to generate oxygen shortages has become more useful than traditional approaches. At low temperatures, CaH₂ decomposes and releases highly active hydrogen atoms. The reduced nanoparticles have a crystalline core/amorphous shell structure and outperform commercial P25 TiO₂ in photocatalytic water purification and photo electrochemical water splitting by 2.4 times and 4.5 times, respectively.

Fig 5: Schematic diagram of Solar water evaporator[21]

They discovered that as the amount of magnesium in TiO₂ grows, the oxygen concentration falls, increasing liquid absorption and darkening the contaminant's colour from white to black. They discovered that black TiO₂ efficiently generates water vapour with solar thermal conversion as high as 50% under solar simulated light irradiation of 1000Wm⁻² when tested in a solar water evaporator [21]

They demonstrated the applicability of black TiO₂ for water evaporation by coating and super hydrophilizing it on an SS mesh. The degree of TiO₂ reduction affects the efficiency of converting solar light energy to heat. They discovered that the higher the TiO₂ reduction, the higher the Ti/O ratio, the blacker the TiO₂, and the better the solar energy to water evaporation conversion efficiency, the higher the TiO₂ reduction, the higher the Ti/O ratio, the blacker the TiO₂, and the better the solar energy to water evaporation conversion efficiency.

They proposed using this low-cost, low-toxic, high-thermal-conversion-efficiency, chemically stable Black TiO₂ to convert solar energy to thermal energy for evaporation of sea or brackish water in areas where drinking water is scarce.[8]

Fig 4: Photographs of synthesize P25, T300 and T400[24]

They found that Reduction at 300°C result in grey colour TiO₂, denoted as T300 and reduction at 400°C result in black colour TiO₂, denoted as T400. The band gap of pristine TiO₂ was approximately 3.2 eV but after CaH₂ reduction it exhibit enhanced visible light absorption of visible light and corresponding band gap was 3.05 eV. They also claim that T400 absorbs 81 percent of solar radiation, which is significantly more than pristine TiO₂. They discovered that treating TiO₂ with CaH₂ lowers the Rutile ratio and causes flaws and an amorphous shell. The low temperature decreased samples' photocatalytic organic degradation and water-splitting capabilities are both superior to those of P25. In addition, CaH₂ reduction improves electron concentration and photo electrochemical water-splitting capabilities significantly.

➤ *Magnesium Reduction Method*

Miaomiao Ye et.al [25] reported synthesis of Black TiO₂ by magnesium (Mg) reduction of white pristine P25 TiO₂ nanocrystals followed by removal of excess Mg with aqueous HCl and Distilled water.

➤ Aluminium reduction

Fig 6: Photograph of BaTiO₃ and black BTO-800[26]

Wang et. al [26] described a method for producing black TiO₂ nanoparticles from molten aluminium using an evacuated two-zone vacuum furnace. They demonstrated that the absorption of visible light and near infrared light is improved by their crystalline core amorphous structure. By reducing aluminium at various temperatures, Zhu et al. created black brookite TiO₂. They discovered that deforming the shell and adding oxygen vacancies and Ti⁺³ states increased photocatalytic activity and light absorption.

C. One step reduction reduction/crystallization process

Fig 7: Schematic structure of P25 and black TiO₂[27]

Alberto Naldoni et. al [27] reported one step reduction process for synthesis of Black TiO₂. Black TiO₂ powder was obtained by heating of titanium precursor under hydrogen stream followed by fast cooling in inert environment until room temperature. They proved that process exhibit a bandgap of only 1.85 eV which matches well with visible light absorption.

D. Argon Treatment

Zhang et. al [28] reported synthesis of Black TiO₂ by argon treatment of sol gel derived Ni doped TiO₂. The Ni doped TiO₂ was mixed with NaBH₄ and heated at 350°C under atmosphere for 1 h followed by cooling at room temperature. The various samples based on amount of Ni such as 0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0 mol% were denoted as MO, M1, M2, M3 and M4. These materials turned black when treated under Argon atmosphere and were denoted as b-MO, b-M1, b-M2, b-M3, b-M4 respectively. Grabstanowicz et. al [29] prepared black TiO₂ powders using two step strategy. The titanium precursor TiH₂ was mixed with H₂O₂ to get slurry. The slurry turned yellow on vacuum desiccation followed by drying at 110°C. Finally yellow powder turns black when heated at 630°C for 3 h in argon atmosphere. They found that synthesize material exhibited larger absorption in the visible and near infrared regions compared to normal TiO₂.

E. High/Low pressure Hydrogen treatment

Chen et. al [30] described the synthesis of black TiO₂ by hydrogenating crystalline TiO₂ at a high pressure of 20 bar for 5 days at 200°C in an H₂ environment. They discovered that the creation of a disordered layer on the surface of black TiO₂ lowered the band gap, which was favourable for carrier trapping. Sun et al. reported synthesis of hydrogenated Black TiO₂ from anatase TiO₂ nanocrystals under high hydrogen pressure. They used an automated sievert's setup to examine the hydrogen adsorption and desorption properties.

Leshuk et. al [30] reported hydrogenation of pristine TiO₂ at different temperatures. They observed the color change and wavelength absorption for a sample which was hydrogenated at 450°C under 20 bar pressure for 24 h. Lu et. al synthesize black titanium dioxide at ambient temperature under high pressure by H₂ treatment on commercial P25. They found that color of P25 turned black after 20 days of hydrogenation also the optical absorption of synthesize material was about 1.0 eV which was lower compared to P25.

F. One Pot Gel Combustion method

Fig 8: Schematic illustration of one pot gel combustion method [31]

Ullatil and Periyat et.al [31] reported synthesis of black TiO_2 via one pot gel combustion method. They synthesize self doped black anatase titanium dioxide using hydroxylation of titanium glycolate gel followed by Calcination at 300°C for 2 hours. They proved that the defective anatase TiO_2 were comprised of Ti^{3+} and oxygen vacancy sites. Thus synthesized material is 33% more photo catalytically active than Degussa-P25

G. Modified Sol gel method

Ting Wang et. al [32] reported facile synthesis of Black TiO_2 with modified sol gel method assisted with CTAB template agent. In this synthesis 5 ml of tetrabutyl titanate were added into 20 ml anhydrous ethanol and light yellow solution was formed. Then 0.5 g CTAB were dissolved into 10 ml of ethanol. The solution was added into light yellow solution under continuous stirring to form a yellow sol. It heated at 180°C for 4 h. The powder obtained was designated as $\text{TiO}_2\text{-CTAB}$. In order to eliminate the residual CTAB molecules, $\text{TiO}_2\text{-CTAB}$ was further calcined at 300°C for 1 h, and black TiO_2 powders were obtained and designated as $\text{TiO}_2\text{CTAB-}300^\circ\text{C}$.

They suggested that CTAB played versatile role of not only altering morphology and structure of TiO_2 nanoparticles but also promoting the generation of V_o and improving the visible light absorption. There are large amounts of V_o in the $\text{TiO}_2\text{CTAB-}300^\circ\text{C}$ nanoparticles, which lead to its strong visible absorption. $\text{TiO}_2\text{CTAB-}300^\circ\text{C}$ catalyst showed efficient photocatalytic activity under visible light irradiation, and giving a H_2 generation of $620 \mu\text{mol/g}$, which was three times higher than control TiO_2 ($210 \mu\text{mol/g}$).

H. ZnCl_2/KCl molten salt assisted synthesis

Jijian Xu et. al [28] reported facile high yield ZnCl_2/KCl molten salt route for synthesis of black titania hexagonal nanosheets by oxidizing TiH_2 in ZnCl_2/KCl salt melt under atmospheric pressure and low temperature 400°C . They suggested that Black titania possesses a tunable phase composition and enhance visible light photocatalytic activity accompanied with a controllable morphology transformation from hexagonal nanosheets to nanorods.

Fig 9: Photograph of black TiO_2 synthesized at various temperatures [28]

I. Hydrogen plasma assisted Chemical Vapor Deposition

Feng Teng et. al [33] reported Preparation of black TiO_2 by hydrogen plasma assisted chemical vapor deposition. 2 g of P25 powder (Degussa) was stirred for 10 min with 50 ml of sodium hydroxide solution in beaker. The obtained solution was transferred into Teflon lined stainless steel autoclave with an inner volume of 40 ml and the autoclave has been sealed and placed in an oven before the oven was heated to 120°C for 12 h. The resultant precipitate was washed with HCl followed by washing using deionized water to attain a PH between 6 and 7. Prepared powder was dried at 110°C .

J. TiO_2 coated plastic sheets

Sutisnaa, Edy Wibowoa, [34] carried out experiment based on, ***TiO₂ coated plastic sheets***. Which have been used to degrade batik wastewater under solar exposure. They have mainly focussed on and experimented on (BOD, COD, TSS), Total of 8 pieces of catalyst sheets are added on 1000 ml of the waste, and managed to degrade 50.41% of the initial concentration during 5-days irradiation respectively.

Fig 10: Experimental setup of Batik waste water treatment. [35]

K. Treatment of waste water using TiO₂ photocatalyst

Suman Dutta , [36](ISM) DHANBAD, INDIA has conducted a detailed study on topics such as waste water treatment utilising TiO₂ based photo catalysts, photocatalyst mechanism, reaction mechanism, and types of photoreactors that can be used. Our main focus, however, is on (Modification of photocatalyst).

Fig 11: Schematic depiction of the floating photocatalyst [36]

L. Coating of TiO₂ on plastic sheets using spray method

F D Utami, D Y Rahman [37] has prepared TiO₂ coated on transparent plastic sheet using (Spray method). The method was employed to degrade organic wastewater (Methylene Blue) under solar exposure. And they have achieved 98% of result in 16 hours of irradiation for A total of 300 blue

Fig 12; TiO₂/Plastic cylinder catalysts (left) and Photocatalyst test (right) [37]

M. Titration co-precipitation

Mike Agbesi Acheampong and Duke Mensah Bonsu Antwi [38] worked on a titration co-precipitation approach followed by Titanium dioxide coating using the sol-gel method. Magnetic Fe₃O₄ nanomagnetic particles must be synthesized. By reducing phosphate, nitrate, and decolorizing methyl blue solutions, they tested numerous different produced TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ nanomagnetic particles with varied molar ratios of TiO₂ to Fe₃O₄. They discovered that TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ particles are good at removing phosphate, nitrate, and methyl blue from wastewater.

N. Sol gel Method

YONGFA ZHU, LI ZHANG[39] experimented on SOL-GEL method and found that Nanosized TiO₂ powder with anatase structure is synthesized using TiCl₄ ethanol solution as a precursor. And they also found that the formation of inorganic gel and anatase TiO₂ nano particles can be promoted by increasing the gelatinizing time.

Fig 13 : The typical TEM photographs of TiO₂ powder gelatinizing for various time and calcined for 1 hour at 400°C.[39]

O. Modified sol gel method

Sanjay Gopal Ullattil and Pradeepan Periyat[40] explicitly stated about the basic principles of sol–gel processing and their advantages / disadvantages, concentrating on the synthesis of nanocrystalline TiO₂. And they also found that from the , three different crystal forms of TiO₂, anatase, rutile and brookite, more photo catalytically active anatase phase is usually converted into rutile phase at low temperature, limiting the high-temperature applications of anatase. And they found that anatase possesses high temperature stability compared to others forms.

Fig 14: Schematic representation of sol–gel processing / Various Steps in Sol–Gel [40]Processing

P. Critical Review table

Table 2 Different Methods for synthesis of Black TiO₂ and their precursors and Performance

Name	Synthetic Route	Precursors	Performance	Ref
Black TiO₂	One pot gel combustion method	Titanium Butoxide and Diethylene glycol	The black TiO ₂ is 33% more Photoactive than Degussa P-25	
Ti⁺³ self doped TiO₂	NaBH ₄ Reduction	Tetra butyl titanate, NaBH ₄ , Ethanol and Nitric acid	For enhanced visible light absorption, Ti ⁺³ generation is responsible	[22]
Black TiO₂	Sol gel method	Tetra butyl titanate, CTAB, Ethanol	H ₂ generation of 620 μmol/g, which was three times higher than control TiO ₂ (210 μmol/g), seen to be given by Black TiO ₂ photocatalyst	[32]
Reduced Black TiO₂	Magnesiothermic reduction	Titanium chloride, Magnesium	The Black TiO ₂ shows remarkable hydrogen production ability in the presence of Pt as a co-catalyst. And as compared to precious reported black this values are superior	[33]
Hydrogenated Black TiO₂	Hydrogenation	Titanium tetraisopropoxide, ethane, deionized water	As solar energy increased Hydrogen production increases.	[38]
Black TiO₂	Oxidation and calcination	TiH ₂ , ZnCl ₂ /KCl, ethanol	The Black titanium shows better photocatalytic activity than P25	[22]
Black TiO₂	Anodization method	Titanium foils, Acetone, Ethanol	The black TiO ₂ is 33% more Photoactive than Degussa P-25	[24]
Laser modified black TiO₂	Ultrasonic treatment	Anatase TiO ₂ , distilled water	It absorb full visible light spectrum and thus exhibit good photocatalytic activity	[39]
Black TiO₂	Flame aerosol process	Titanium isopropoxide, silver acetate, 2-ethyl hexanoic acid, acetonitrile	Crystalline Ti-suboxide onto Ag nanoparticles supported on nano-structured exhibit strong activity under visible light	[28]
Black TiO₂	Hydrogenation	TiH ₂ , Ethanol		[13]
Ordered Mesoporous Black TiO₂	Evaporation induced self assembly method	Tetrabutyl titanate, Ethanol, HCl, Ethylenediamine	Ordered mesoporous Black TiO ₂ has wide pore size and Surface area compared to Mesoporous white TiO ₂	[10]
Coper doped TiO₂	Complex Precipitation method	Copper nitrate trihydrate, Glycerol, Anatase TiO ₂	Catalyst prepared by 10% copper loading shows better activity than Wet impregnation method	[21]
Black TiO₂	Chemical vapor deposition assisted by Hydrogen plasma	P25 powder (Degussa), NaOH, HCl	Disordered layer is formed after hydrogen plasma treatment, in black TiO ₂ which may be caused by numerous oxygen vacancies and Ti-H bonds	[33]
Reduced Black TiO₂	Facile hydrothermal Approach	TiCl ₃ , L- ascorbic acid, NaOH	When compared to the white (20.6 mol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹) and brown TiO ₂ (38.9 mol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹), the black TiO ₂ has a far higher activity with a hydrogen evolution rate of 116 mol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ .	[34]
N doped yellow TiO₂	Hydrolysis and Calcination	Titanium tetraisopropoxide, Urea	N-doped TiO ₂ powders obtained by heating Ti(OH) ₄ with urea exhibit similar activity to TiO ₂ powders prepared by heating TiO ₂ with Urea. which also responds on visible light.	[21]

Carbon modified TiO₂	Hydrolysis, aging, drying and Calcination	Titanium tetrachloride, Tetra butyl ammonium hydroxide, Sodium hydroxide and Glucose	A good activity for degradation of 4-chlorophenol is exhibited by these photocatalyst which get well absorbed into visible to infrared region up to 800 nm.	[22]
Black TiO₂	Ultrasonication process	Titanium sulfate , ammonia	TiO ₂ prepared by this method with applying changes in structure and DOS of amorphous hydroxylated shows both activities such as solar driven and visible light driven	[23]

III. CONCLUSIONS

The synthesis, characteristics, alterations, and applications of TiO₂ nanoparticles have all been extensively studied in recent decades, yielding a large database. New features and applications with increased performance have been introduced thanks to advancements in TiO₂ nanomaterial production. We infer from our evaluation of studies that each synthesis method has its own unique and particular requirements that distinguish it from the others. as an example, The major benefits of the sol-gel method include the ability to prepare sols and gels at room temperature, high purity of precursors, product homogeneity, low sintering temperatures, and good control over powder particle size and form. Chemical reduction methods include reducing TiO₂ with active hydrogen species like hydrogen ions or hydrogen atoms with H₂ or H₂/Ar or hydrogen atoms with N₂, using high temperatures with active metals like aluminium, magnesium, and zinc powder, or reducing TiO₂ in solution with NaBH₄ and organic molecules like imidazole and ascorbic acid. It has been created a one-pot gel combustion of black anatase TiO_{2-x} self-doped with Ti³⁺. Anatase TiO₂ nanocrystals include large Ti³⁺ and oxygen vacancy sites, which have been thought to be important components for photocatalysis. According to the findings, black anatase TiO₂ had 33 percent more photoactivity than Degussa-P25, a widely available photocatalyst. The photocatalytic features of white TiO₂ include the fact that it cannot absorb visible light and so has a lower photo conversion efficiency. It has poor charge separation ability due to its short light response range and low efficiency.

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